

CDA NEWSLETTER

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CDA
BAYERO UNIVERSITY
KANO

**CENTRE FOR
DRYLAND AGRICULTURE**
AN AFRICA CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

CORE VALUES

- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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CDA Splashes N7.5 million to Young Entrepreneurs for Winning Maiden AgriHacking Competition

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano has rewarded five young entrepreneurs with N7.5 million to set up business enterprises for pitching their innovative Agri-business plans and investment models.

Besides, the brilliant business starters would also, among other benefits, be exposed to agribusiness mentorship and knowledge development at the CDA to further broaden their capacity to grow their products and market base.

Announcing the winner at the CDA 2nd Open Day for Exhibition and Awards Presentation of the AgriHacking, Head of the judges and former Director in the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, Hajiya Karimatu Babangida, said the overall best Hafzeema Enterprise scored 60.5 points to claim the start price of N2 million, while Zukogi Ideolated Cooking Oil who scored 60 points clinched the second position with N1,750,000.

Hajiya Babangida hinted that Stem Innovation Hub, Miraco Farms, and AG Dried Tomatoes Flours clinched the third, fourth, and fifth positions respectively. According to the lead jury, the contestants were judged based on their ability to defend their production, teamwork, business model, impact, innovation, credibility, and market viability of their products.

Unveiling the rationale behind the AgriHacking 1.0, the Director, CDA, Bayero University, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin revealed that the motive was to facilitate brilliant ideas in young and innovative talents in the agribusiness ecosystem to provide solutions to food security in the country.

"CDA over the years has made significant impacts in the area of academic and research development but we believe we can also support young innovators who need a little notch in their entrepreneurship to create more wealth and solve challenges in food production.

"And more importantly, the winners would also be supported with mentorship and connect them with the market where they grow their businesses from strength to strengthen". Prof. Jibrin noted.

Representative of Hafzeema Enterprise, the star prize winner, Halimatu Sagir Musa, applauded the CDA for the support and enabling environment for the young entrepreneurs to showcase their wealth of business ideas.

She stressed that the money support and mentorship would further widen their production and market viability and create more job opportunities for teaming youths.

During the opening session of the AgriHacking 1.0 challenge, the Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, who was represented by the Deputy Vice Chancellor, Academics, Professor Muhammad Sani Gumel, said "we are proud of the strides we have made in improving our innovation ecosystem, but we know that there is still much work to be done. We will continue to invest in research and development and encourage our students to develop innovative solutions to our society's challenges."

Goodwill messages were presented by Professor Murtala Sagagi, former Special Assistant to former Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development, and Professor Luis Mira Da Silva. President of Agripreneurship Alliance, Dr. Anne Roulin delivered a keynote address.

The AgriHacking took place on Monday, 8th May, 2023.

CDA over the years has made significant impacts in the area of academic and research development but we believe we can also support young innovators who need a little notch in their entrepreneurship to create more wealth and solve challenges in food production

DVC Academics, Prof Sani M. Gumel (right), Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (middle), Chairperson SIAB of CDA, Haj Karimatu Babangida (left) and other dignitaries observing the National Anthem

DVC Academics, Prof Sani M. Gumel (right), Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (middle) and Chairperson SIAB of CDA Haj Karimatu Babangida

Winner of Quizz competition, Najib Sanusi Gaya (left) receiving CDA customized T-shirt from Director, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (middle), while Dr MMB assists

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The contribution of spices to sustainable agricultural development globally is enormous with promising potential in the area of food, medicine and pharmaceuticals.

- Customers generally look for more natural and healthier products including spices, they are now more conscious and conscious about products origins and production process.
- Spice adulteration is mostly attributed to rising demand for exotic herbs and spices and a supply constraint. Spices have become more vulnerable to adulteration whether planned or intentional, since the international trade has grown tremendously.
- Deliberate adulteration is usually motivated by a desire to maximize profit margins.
- Spices and herbs can be swapped with other plants or artificial colors and unlisted flavoring can be added, sometimes spices are adulterated with chalk powder, brick powder and some toxic substances are added to gain profit and lower cost so as to compete with market.

Team lead of Hafzeema Enterprizes presenting business idea of the team

Prof Bala Ado Kofar Mata (right) and Haj Karimatu Babangida serving as judges

Team Hadeekatul Khairat Garden

Director of CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin, presenting welcome address

DVC Management Services, Prof M.U Sani (l) and other dignitaries impressed with CDA farm produce, while Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (r) explains further

CDA Organizes 2nd Open Day, Sets Target to Address Developmental Challenges in Africa's Dryland Regions

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University Kano on Tuesday, 9th May 2023 organized its second Open Day for exhibition and set out targets to address challenges in Dryland Agriculture in Africa essentially as it affects food production and security office in the continent.

Besides that, the Centre outlines a commitment to sustain quality development of innovation and technology while focusing on training and research to build capacity for Dryland production.

CDA Director, Professor Jibrin Mohammad Jibrin gave the disclosure at the center's second

annual open day celebration organized to showcase its modest innovation and technical breakthroughs over the years.

Professor Jibrin noted that CDA has excelled significantly in the area of knowledge transfer and research development adding that its commitment to Dryland production attracted resources and funding from World Bank and French Agency for Development (AGD).

While revealing that CDA has trained over 530 PhD and MSc students majority drawn from 15 African countries, Professor Jibrin added that the CDA has several formidable networks of partnership with international and regional

institutions with common interests.

"The Centre plans to establish a regional Innovation, training, and Entrepreneurship hub where youth will be trained in modern intensive agriculture and in bioresource entrepreneurship. This is aimed at facilitating the emergence of small and medium scale enterprises that will help in alleviating poverty and improve livelihood in the inhabitants of the sub-region".

Vice Chancellor Bayero University Kano, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, who was represented by Deputy Vice Chancellor, Management Services, Professor Mahmud Umar Sani, revealed that the CDA has no doubt been a trailblazer among the research centres of the university and that the Centre has already positioned itself as a regional centre of excellence in dryland agriculture, fulfilling its vision of becoming an Africa centre of excellence under the auspices of the World Bank and the French Development Agency.

The Vice Chancellor added that while the CDA remains a regional centre of excellence through consistent innovation and technological development, he assured the university's readiness to support the CDA with the necessary atmosphere that enables it to strive to greater heights.

Part of the activities featured at the open day includes exhibition of farm produce of the CDA, other achievements facilitated by the regional centre of excellence and showcase of products of its partners. The occasion also witnessed reward of hard work and excellent performance of both junior and senior staff with awards presentations.

Similarly, CDA used the occasion to reward five young entrepreneurs who showcased the best agribusiness plan and investment model pitch in the maiden edition of its maiden AgriHacking 1.0 program held earlier.

Dignitaries impressed with the explanation about products being exhibited

Teams that participated at the AgriHacking challenge with the dignitaries

Mr Deji Hameed Ajani signing MoU between Opolo Global and CDA in the presence of DVC M.S, Prof M.U Sani and Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin

DVC M.S. Prof M.U Sani (left) signing MoU between CDA and Opolo Global in the presence of Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin

Dignitaries inspecting products exhibited at the 2nd CDA Open Day

Hajiya Sugura Mahmud (l) and Chairperson CDA SIAB, Hajiya Karimatu Babangida (r)

VC Leads CDA Team at 9th Regional ACE-Impact Workshop in Marrakech, Morocco

Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas has led the team from Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) to participate at the 9th Africa Centres of Excellence Project regional workshop in Marrakech, Morocco.

The workshop which took place from 29th May to 2nd June 2023 had the objectives of Fostering cross-country partnerships and networks between centres and Moroccan higher education institutions and private sector stakeholders especially on joint research, co-creation of programmes, entrepreneurship, and innovation opportunities and ii) provide opportunities for deep dive training and capacity building on moving research from the laboratories to market.

The workshop was co-organized by the World Bank, French Development Agency, Association of African Universities, University Mohammed VI Polytechnic (UM6P), OCP Africa and Ministry of Higher Education, Morocco.

A key feature of the workshop was the provision of implementation support and fostering partnerships with Moroccan higher education institutions and the private sector.

The objective of the workshop was apt as it is in tandem with the major thrust of the Africa Centre of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture (CDA) which tries to consolidate on the gains and achievements of the Centre in the ACE I project with the renewed

The Director, Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) in a group photograph with some participants at the 9th ACE- Impact regional Workshop. The Executive Secretary of the National Universities Commission, Professor Abubakar Adamu Rasheed

aim of making positive development impact towards attainment of its vision '**Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands**'. Towards achieving this, the CDA leveraged on the meeting to connect (network) with other partner institutions towards ensuring sustainability of the Centre.

At the end of the workshop, the Centre Leader (Director) Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin expressed optimism with the closing remarks of Moustapha El-boushini of UM6P who said, 'this is the beginning of collaboration with sub-Saharan Africa Higher Education towards development impact in the region'.

CDA, Federal Ministry of Agric Train Women and Youth Farmers on Micro Irrigation Scheme

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) and Federal Department of Agriculture of the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) trained women and youth farmers from the North-Eastern part of Nigeria on micro irrigation schemes.

The training was a 3-day capacity building for marginal women and youth organized to capacitate lead farmers invited from different youth and women groups from the vibrant region of North-East with the objective of introducing them to various types of irrigation systems such as drip and sprinkler technologies and equipping them with the necessary skills to set them up effectively.

According to the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, who presented a welcome address, said CDA is working with various partners including FMARD to build the capacity of local farmers. He said as a regional centre of excellence, the CDA has been working to improve the agricultural landscape in West and Central Africa.

The Director, Irrigation and Crop Development in the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, Hajiya Sugura Mahmud said “we are all aware of the challenges facing our nation, particularly in the realms of food security and sustainable

development. With a population of 200 million, Nigeria's demand for food is ever-increasing. It is imperative that we strive for improved agricultural production to meet this demand, reduce our dependence on imports, and foster economic growth."

She urged the participants to actively engage with the facilitators and fellow participants throughout the training. She also seized the opportunity to express my heartfelt appreciation to the principal officers of the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, including the honourable Minister and Minister of State for their

unwavering support in organizing the training.

The training was practical as the participants were exposed to practical demonstrations of drip and sprinkler irrigation facilities in the CDA's modern research and training farm.

The training took place from 9th May to 12th May 2023 at CDA.

It would be recalled that CDA and FMARD organized a similar training from 22nd to 24th March 2021 on *Drip Irrigation Systems and Good Agricultural Practices (GAPs) in Vegetable Production for Irrigation Farming Groups in Kano State* held in CDA.

CDA Organizes Workshop on Intellectual Property Protection

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has organized a one-day workshop on Intellectual Property Protection under the Initiatives for Sustainable Food Security Innovations in the Drylands (IsFOSID). The workshop took place on 13th April 2023.

The Director CDA, professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, who was represented by the Deputy Director, Outreach and Publications, Professor Amina Mustapha said in the last year the CDA has engaged in a series of trainings to develop the capacity of academic staff and other segments of the society. She said intellectual property is sacrosanct to protecting one's original work, saying that this workshop would equip the participants with the right skills to protect their intellectual property.

Director of the Directorate of Research, Innovation, and Partnership (DRIP), Professor I. A. Rufai expressed dismay that the generation of intellectual property is at its lowest ebb, noting that the gathering was to address the problem.

He said globally, universities are ranked based on the patent they are able to produce, adding that Bayero University is doing everything possible to rise to the challenge in producing patents that would address societal problems.

Research, Innovation, and Commercialization: DRIP, CDA Organize Sensitization Workshop

The Directorate of Research, Innovation, and Partnership (DRIP) organized a one-day sensitization workshop on Investment in Research Innovation and Commercialization for National Development.

The workshop was under the Initiatives for Sustainable Food Security Innovations in the Drylands (ISFOSID) project funded by PASET Regional Scholarship and Innovation Fund, which took place at the CDA Conference Hall.

Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas said in line with the vision of Bayero University, Kano,

leading in research and education has stood out as the university's trademark agenda.

The Vice Chancellor, who was represented by the Deputy Vice Chancellor, Academics, Professor Muhammad Sani Gumel commended DRIP and CDA for organizing the workshop, saying that the University remained committed to supporting initiatives that would derive the university's agenda.

Earlier in his welcome address, the Director Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Professor Jibrin Mohammed

Jibrin, who was represented by the Deputy Director, Outreach and Publications, Professor Amina Mustapha, said it was good for the university to start commercialization of its products and services with a view to generating revenue for sustainability.

The Director DRIP, Professor I. A. Rufai said the workshop was apt and timely as it came at the time when the University was devising new strategies for alternative sources of revenue for growth and development.

World Food Programme Officials Visit CDA, Initiate Discussions for Collaboration

Officials from World Food Programme Country Office, Abuja on 5th May 2023 paid a courtesy call on the Management of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA). The officials led by Epimacque Nsanzababanwa said they were impressed with the CDA's milestone and would be open to collaborations in many aspects

Mr Nsanzababanwa, who is a Rwandan national said CDA and World Food Programme have many things in common add as such CDA would be a strong partner in the area of food production and research activities.

Welcoming the visitors, the Director CDA, professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin gave a brief background of the Centre and expressed happiness over the visit. He expressed the determination and readiness of the Centre to enter into a collaborative engagement with the World Food Programme to boost food production in Africa.

The visit was facilitated by the Programme Director of Centre for Community Development and Research Network, Abba Isyaku Adamu, who recommended that CDA and WFP have many things in common and their collaboration would yield positive dividends in addressing the challenges of food insecurity in Africa.

CDA Celebrates Sallah with Regional Students

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has celebrated Eid-el-Kabir with its regional students as part of its effort to strengthen relationships with students.

The regional students who were visibly elated with the goodwill gesture of CDA, remarked that the Sallah celebration was well spent as they ate the famous Sallah meat and interacted with their supervisors and colleagues.

Celestin Thiombiano, PhD student from Burkina Faso expressed gratitude to the CDA for organizing such a reception in their honour and said that the joy and happiness could not be overemphasized. "Today is our Sallah and we are enjoying it with every sense of happiness and glamour," he said.

"It was quite a rewarding experience to sit and eat with the CDA staff. We have learned a lot and even after going back home, we will keep something in our mind about what CDA did to us. The network would indeed be fruitful and

beneficial, said Paulo Goba, a PhD student of Natural Resources Management and Climate Change from Mozambique.

A PhD student from Ethiopia, Fenet Belay, said they had really enjoyed the meat and the food provided by the CDA, saying that the Ethiopians wished all Muslims happy Eid-el-Kabir celebrations.

Tumano Djaidja from Cameroun said she must thank the CDA for organizing the Sallah celebration and said they enjoyed every moment of the get-together organized by the centre. She congratulated the Muslim community for celebrating the festive period.

Zainab I. Drame from Mali, who studies PhD in Livelihood and Natural Resources Economics, said all the regional students are happy with the positive treatment with the CDA, and organizing the Sallah celebration to eat and drink with the staff was another important step to streamline the already established positive relationship.

Maimuna Nahaman, a PhD student of Natural Resources Management and Climate from Niger Republic was full of praises to the CDA staff whom she said have been making their stay in Nigeria easier. She expressed their gratitude for the cordial relationship between teachers and students.

Another PhD student of Natural Resources Management and Climate Change from Senegal, Momath Diankha CDA gave them a positive impression the first day they came to Nigeria. He said coming together to celebrate Sallah showed how they were highly valued and respected. He said on behalf of all Senegalese students, they remained indebted to the CDA.

While welcoming the regional students earlier, the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, said the Centre has organized the ceremony for the regional students to share the moment of the festive period.

The Director, who was represented by the CDA-ACE Project Manager, Dr. Yusuf Garba, said it was not a moment of long speech, but an avenue to eat food and meat and interact with one another. He said the CDA felt that it was paramount to bring the regional students together to celebrate the Sallah with their supervisors and CDA staff as part of the Centre's effort in boosting relationships with the students.

He further called on the students to network among themselves since they have come from different countries.

The ceremony took place on Thursday, 29th June 2023 at the entrance of M-Block, Old Campus

Present at the occasion were Dr. Yusuf Garba, Dr. Murtala Muhammad Badamasi, Dr. Aminu Fagge, Dr. Amina L. Mustapha, Abbas Liman, Aliyu Sani Zubairu, and Communications Officer, Nura Garba.

UK-Based Quality Assurance Agency Evaluates BUK Programmes for International Accreditation

A united Kingdom-based Quality Assurance Agency has evaluated Bayero University, Kano programmes for international accreditation.

The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education, usually referred to simply as the Quality Assurance Agency or **QAA** is the UK higher education sector's independent expert quality body, with a remit to maintain and

enhance the quality of teaching and learning in tertiary education in the UK and beyond. It conducts quality assessment reviews, develops reference points and guidance for providers, and conducts or commissions research on relevant issues.

The QAA experts, Julian Ellis and Dr. Yue Song conducted various sessions of question and answer on the university's programmes, teacher-student relationship, accreditation, academic planning, and programme review among others.

They had sessions with the university management, staff, and students as well as sessions on the physical infrastructures, laboratory equipment and many others.

Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas while responding to questions from QAA, said Bayero University has grown in leaps and bounds with 15 research centres, 18 faculties, 92 departments, 99 undergraduate programmes, 25 part-time undergraduate programmes, and 200 postgraduate programmes. He said the University has a total of 45,810 students.

The University he said was ranked as the 4th best university in Nigeria by the Times Higher Education, UK, and 1,016 globally.

He explained that whatever the university is doing, it follows the due process and laid down procedure either in programme review, accreditation exercise, staff recruitment or examinations.

The Vice Chancellor told the QAA experts that the University has a number of collaborations and partnerships with institutions, corporate bodies, and agencies especially in Europe and they are conducting joint research activities together/ He added that Bayero University has students from many countries in West and Central Africa and other regions.

On choosing QAA to evaluate and accredit the University programmes, the Vice Chancellor said international quality review ensures that institutions meet and maintain the

international standard and the review helps potential students and their families to have a certain level of trust in the institution.

He said accreditation leads to accountability and higher levels of quality education and that meeting standards attract new students and more collaborators.

There had been a virtual tour of facilities that include physical infrastructure, laboratory

equipment, and recreation centres, during which the Deputy Vice Chancellor, Academics, Professor Sani Mohammed Gumel made a presentation and responded to questions asked.

Other questions were answered by the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, Director Academic Planning, Professor Haruna Musa and Deputy Director Strategic Planning and Monitoring, Directorate of Academic Planning, Dr. Yusuf Garba.

The accreditation was facilitated by

the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) and the Africa Centre for Population Health and Policy (ACEPHAP) led by the Directorate of Academic Planning Director CDA, Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin as part of the mandate of Disbursement Linked Indicators (DLI 7) by the World Bank which calls for Africa Centres of Excellence to drive international accreditation in their institutions.

Bayero University has grown in leaps and bounds with 15 research centres, 18 faculties, 92 departments, 99 undergraduate programmes, 25 part-time undergraduate programmes, and 200 postgraduate programmes, with a total number of 45,810 students. The University was ranked as the 4th best university in Nigeria by the Times Higher Education, UK, and 1,016 globally

BUK Holds Regional Strategy Validation Workshop Facilitated by CDA and ACEPHAP

Bayero University, Kano on 20th June 2023 held a Regional Strategy Validation Workshop on ratification of Disbursement Linked Indicator No. 7 designed by the World Bank and Association of African Universities for institutional impact.

The workshop was aimed at presenting the Draft report of the Regional Strategy document for achieving the Disbursement Linked Indicator 7.1 with a view to making a comprehensive observation, providing input, and ratifying it by the key stakeholders of the University.

The Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, who presented the DLI 7 document, said part of the requirements of the World Bank is that the Africa Centres of Excellence (ACEs) must positively impact their institutions. He said the broad objective is to impart high quality training, strengthen and build regional partnerships and conduct high impact research to address Africa's developmental challenges.

The Vice Chancellor, who was represented by the Deputy Vice Chancellor, Management Services, Professor Mahmud

Management. He said the two ACEs in BUK, the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) and the Africa Centre of Excellence for Population Health and Policy (ACEPHAP) enjoy the full support of the management in view of their performance and achievements.

Prof Abbas noted that the regional strategy document would be applied to all aspects of the university stressing that it is not for the consumption of the ACEs alone. He commended the committee headed by Professor Mustapha Ahmad Isa for a job well done in drafting the document.

The Chairman of the Draft Committee, Professor Isa said the committee was to review the functions and activities of the CDA and ACEPHAP and then draft a document for achieving the DLI 7. He said part of the activities of the committee was to organize the workshop to get feedback from stakeholders involved directly or indirectly in the activities of those centres.

The CDA Deputy Director for Outreach and Publications Professor Amina Mustapha presented the Draft Regional Strategy 2023-2028. The stakeholders took the time to provide input and make valid suggestions on how to improve the document.

Earlier in his welcome address, the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, who was represented by the Deputy Director Training of the CDA, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed welcomed all the stakeholders to the CDA Conference Hall, the venue of the workshop and said it was highly important workshop owing to the provision of the DLI 7 requirement that the ACEs ought to achieve.

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The New Regional Director of Africa for ICRISAT, Dr. Rebbie Phiri Harewa on 20th June 2023 visited Bayero University, Kano on her first official tour to the institution and described the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) as one of ICRISAT's best strategic partners.

The visit according to her was to strengthen the collaboration between the CDA and ICRISAT which has yielded positive results over the years. She said it was also necessary in view of the CDA's strategic importance and the role it plays in addressing the challenges of Africa's drylands.

The Regional Director said CDA and ICRISAT should have a renewed collaboration on crop

CDA One of ICRISAT's Strategic Partners, Director Africa Says

improvement, resilient farming, and food security in Africa, noting that the two institutions can significantly impact Africa.

"Listening to you gives me a glimmer of hope that CDA is

one of our trusted partners in Africa and that we can effectively strengthen our partnership to make an impact in Africa.," said the visiting Director of Africa.

According to her the CDA and ICRISAT would work on the improvement of the agricultural value chain in Africa. She noted that the value chain has almost collapsed in the region, but with the expertise and technology, the system would be revived

The Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, who was represented by the Deputy Director, Training, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed said that ICRISAT is the best international partner of CDA with which the

centre had accomplished many things in the past. He recalled that in June last year, a CDA Team led by the Director visited the ICRISAT Headquarters at Patancheru, India. The team was received by Dr. Jacqueline d'Arros Hughes, the Director General of ICRISAT; Dr Arvind Kumar, Deputy Director General Research, Program Directors, Dr. Victor Afarisefa, Dr. Sreenath Dixit and senior ICRISAT scientific staff.

The Director welcomed renewed collaborative areas with ICRISAT and expressed the CDA'S readiness and determination to continue to work with ICRISAT to address major Africa's developmental challenges.

The new Regional Director was accompanied by the ICRISAT Country Director, Dr. Ignatius Angarawai, and the Accountant of the Institute, Abdullahi Bashir, while other CDA team members at the visit were Dr. Aminu Fagge, Abbas Liman, Dr. Amina Lawan Mustapha and the Communications Officer, Nura Garba.

Listening to you gives me a glimmer of hope that CDA is one of our trusted partners in Africa and that we can effectively strengthen our partnership to make an impact in Africa

CDA Organizes Orientation for its PG Students, Conducts Training on Proposal Writing

Center for Dryland Agriculture has organized an orientation program for its postgraduate students to enlighten and acquaint them with the necessary procedures, rules, and regulations governing their stay in the University.

The orientation program which took place on 13th June 2023 at the CDA Conference Hall, was also meant to familiarize the students with campus life, postgraduate study guidelines, available

resources, and the university's policies.

In his address, the Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin said the ceremony was delayed due to some unforeseen circumstances, but urged the students to learn the landscape of the university, utilize the resources available, and know the guidelines of postgraduate studies in order to have a smooth and successful academic journey.

The Dean of Postgraduate Studies of BUK, Professor Mustapha Ahmad Isa spoke on the roles of the School for Postgraduate Studies (SPS) at BUK. He advised the students to always read the student handbook and make it their companion.

In his presentation on an Overview of the Training in CDA, the Deputy Director Training of the Centre, Prof. Sanusi G. Mohammed said, CDA runs 10 postgraduate programmes with 5 MScs, 4 PhDs, and 1 Postgraduate diploma. He also added that the Centre conducts short courses in which over 3000 people were recently trained on various agricultural value chains in addition to training women on fish spawning in Maradi, Niger Republic. He said the CDA conducted a short training in Ghana last year.

The CDA also trained its postgraduate students on proposal writing and literature review. The training was organized for students from CDA-supported programmes of Natural Resources Management and, Climate Change, Crops, and Cropping Systems, Range and Livestock Management in Drylands, and Livelihood and Natural Resource Economics.

The aim of the training was to equip the students with the methods of writing a good proposal and thesis writing.

Presentations were made by the Director of the Directorate of Research, Innovation, and Partnership, Professor I. A. Rufai, Dr. Munir Kamba, Dr. Yusuf Garba, Dr. Murtala Muhammad Badamasi, Dr. Muhammad Maina, Dr. Kabir Umar Mustapha and a host of others.

There were practical sessions to assess the level of understanding of the students.

The training and orientation took place from 13th to 15th June 2023.

CDA Organizes Training on Grant Writing and Management

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has taken a proactive step in advancing capacity building within the University by organizing a comprehensive 5-Day training on Grant Writing and Management. The training, which took place from Monday, 3rd to Friday, 7th July 2023, was aimed at enhancing the capabilities of academic staff from various centres and directorates of the university. The objective was to equip them with the necessary skills to craft compelling proposals that would attract research grants and funding.

The training not only focused on improving the staff's ability to meet the requirements of research proposals domestically and internationally but also aimed at strengthening

their overall proficiency in responding to the ever-evolving landscape of grant writing skills including mapping funders, tracking calls, consortium formation, contracting and research budgeting, as well as overall grants-ship management skills.

The ACE Partner program of the French Institute of Research and Development (IRD) in collaboration with the Centre for Dryland Agriculture, facilitated the training.

The Senegalese-based Regional Coordinator of IRD, Dr. Mamadou Aliou Diallo, led the training with invaluable support from esteemed individuals such as Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, the Deputy Director, Training at CDA and Dr. Murtala Muhammad Badamasi.

Dr. Diallo emphasized the primary focus of the training was to expose faculty to the silent issues in grant writing and management. He expressed his satisfaction with the participants' positive response and anticipated significant improvement in the grant writing and proposal development ecosystems based on their progress.

During the opening session, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, the Director of CDA,

welcomed the participants and encouraged them to seize this opportunity to enhance their proposal writing skills, which would enable them to create strong proposals capable of securing research grants.

By investing in this capacity-building intervention, the Centre for Dryland Agriculture aims to empower the University staff, enabling them to excel in their research pursuits and secure the necessary funding to drive impactful

STUDENTS IN FOCUS

Research Focus

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